

ISic3175

I.Sicily inscription 3175

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Lucia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di Santa Lucia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329711

1. Καστεῖνα Ῥωμαία
2. ἀγαθὸν ²vestigia litterarum²
3. Καστεῖνα ἐτῶν [— —]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645505

PHI 329711

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 14.0582

Agnello, S.L. 1954. Recenti esplorazioni nelle catacombe siracusane di S. Lucia. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 30: 7-60. At 22 fig.2

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